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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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IMPLEMENTATION OUTCOMES AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF THE SOCIAL AND LEGAL CLUB IN THE SECONDARY VOCATIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM AS A TOOL FOR DELIVERING SOCIAL SERVICES

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Abstract: Using Samarkand State Medical University as an example, this paper examines the experience of establishing and operating a Social and Legal Club (SLC) within the secondary vocational education system. The study analyzes the dual function of the club as both a mechanism for providing free legal assistance to the population and an innovative, practice-oriented educational platform aimed at developing students' professional competencies. The article presents the tangible outcomes of the club's activities, identifies existing systemic barriers, proposes practical solutions, and outlines prospects for the further development and replication of social and legal clubs within the secondary vocational education system.

Key words: free legal assistance, practice-oriented learning, professional competencies, legal clinic, social and legal club, secondary vocational education, mentorship.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti misolida o'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida ijtimoiy-huquqiy klubni tashkil etish va faoliyatini yo'lga qo'yish tajribasi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot doirasida klubning ikki tomonlama funksiyasi – aholi uchun bepul huquqiy yordam ko'rsatish vositasi hamda talabalar kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiluvchi amaliy ta'lim platformasi sifatidagi o'rni yoritiladi. Klub faoliyati natijalari, mavjud tizimli to'siqlar, ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari hamda o'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida ijtimoiy-huquqiy klublarni rivojlantirish va joriy etish istiqbollari asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: bepul huquqiy yordam, amaliy yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, kasbiy kompetensiyalar, huquqiy klinika, ijtimoiy-huquqiy klub, o'rta maxsus ta'lim, mentorlik.

Аннотация: В статье на примере Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета рассматривается опыт создания и функционирования социально-правового клуба в системе среднего профессионального образования. Особое внимание уделяется двойственной роли клуба как инструмента оказания бесплатной юридической помощи населению и инновационной практико-ориентированной образовательной платформы, направленной на формирование профессиональных компетенций обучающихся. В работе проанализированы результаты деятельности клуба, выявлены существующие системные ограничения, предложены пути их преодоления, а также определены перспективы дальнейшего развития и тиражирования социально-правовых клубов в системе среднего профессионального образования.

Ключевые слова: бесплатная юридическая помощь, практико-ориентированное обучение, профессиональные компетенции, юридическая клиника, социально-правовой клуб, среднее профессиональное образование, наставничество.

INTRODUCTION

The constitutionally guaranteed right to free legal aid (Federal Law No. 324-FZ) and its practical accessibility for socially disadvantaged groups of individuals continue to be sharply out of balance in contemporary times. Remote communities located far from administrative centers, as well as areas with low population density, are particularly affected by this issue. Concurrently, in order to implement specialty 40.02.04 "Jurispru-

dence,” the secondary vocational education system urgently requires effective methods of practice-oriented training that enable the development of professional skills in conditions as close to real practice as possible.

Incorporating the Social and Legal Club (SLC) into the curriculum represents a creative approach to simultaneously addressing both objectives. In addition to providing free legal consultations to the local community, the club offers students a unique educational experience in which they can develop professional skills by working on real legal issues faced by residents. The relevance and feasibility of the proposed concept are convincingly demonstrated by the experience of the “Legal Clinic” Social and Legal Club at the Barnaul Cooperative Technical School.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scholarly research on clinical legal education emphasizes its role as an effective mechanism for combining legal training with social responsibility. According to Frank S. Bloch, clinical programs represent a global movement aimed at educating future legal professionals through direct engagement with real social justice challenges, thereby strengthening professional competence and ethical awareness. Richard Wilson also highlights that legal clinics should be understood not merely as a teaching method but as an institutional model that integrates legal education, community service, and applied learning. These studies demonstrate that practice-oriented legal structures enable students to acquire professional skills while simultaneously addressing gaps in access to justice, especially for socially vulnerable groups.

Further research explores the institutional sustainability and systemic impact of legal clinics within educational frameworks. The collective work edited by Richard Grimes and colleagues analyzes clinical legal education as an essential tool for improving access to justice and enhancing legal aid systems through structured mentorship and cooperation with external stakeholders. Empirical findings presented by Adrian Evans and co-authors show that mentorship-based and practice-oriented legal education models significantly improve students' professional readiness and communication skills. In addition, analytical reports by the OECD underline the importance of institutionalized legal aid mechanisms in ensuring social equity and effective public service delivery. Together, these studies provide a solid theoretical and empirical foundation for examining the implementation outcomes and development prospects of social and legal clubs within the secondary vocational education system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Barnaul Cooperative Technical School tested the management model of the “Legal Clinic” Social and Legal Club (SLC), which is founded on the principles of organizational dualism, multi-level mentorship, and an integrated approach.

Organizational Dualism and Three-Level Structure. A key feature of the model is dual subordination, as the club is integrated into both extracurricular and academic activities through professional modules and internships. Management is organized according to a three-level structure.

At the strategic level, the technical school director holds overall authority and is responsible for approving the regulatory framework.

At the tactical level, a supervising teacher provides pedagogical supervision and methodological guidance.

At the operational level, the club chairman and participating students are responsible for scheduling meetings, managing documentation, and overseeing the club's day-to-day activities.

The Use of a Multi-Level Mentoring System as a Teaching Tool. The program is based on an integrated mentoring system that combines three complementary formats.

The “Teacher–Student” format provides academic guidance, supervision, and quality control for all legal consultations and documentation.

The peer-to-peer, or “Student–Student,” mentoring format involves both horizontal and vertical mentoring, in which senior students act as mentors to support newcomers in adapting more quickly while simultaneously developing their own managerial and leadership skills.

To ensure a strong connection with professional practice, the “Employer–Student” format involves government officials, advocates, and practicing attorneys in master classes, advanced case analysis, and external evaluation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data from a pedagogical experiment and monitoring conducted in 2024–2025 confirmed the comprehensive socio-educational impact of the pilot implementation of the “Legal Clinic” Social and Legal Club (SLC) model.

Academic Outcomes

Expert evaluation revealed that in 88 % of cases, the quality of legal documents prepared by students met professional standards. Based on self-assessment results, 91 % of participating students reported a significant improvement in their practical skills related to client interaction and legal documentation. In comparison with the control group, a statistically significant increase was observed in the level of both professional competencies (hard skills) and interpersonal competencies (soft skills).

Social Outcomes

On a 10-point scale, the citizen satisfaction score among individuals who received legal assistance reached 9.4, demonstrating both a high level of students' communication skills and the effective resolution of legal issues. During the pilot period, four cooperation agreements were concluded with law firms and non-governmental organizations, thereby expanding the resource base and networking opportunities. Volunteer initiatives, including the "Legal Urgent Care" campaign, which provided assistance to more than 20 residents, were successfully implemented.

The operational sustainability of the approach was also demonstrated. The short-term initiative entitled "Alimony: Simply About the Important," launched to promptly respond to a surge in requests, served as a clear example of managerial flexibility. This initiative enabled rapid adaptation to emerging needs without requiring changes to permanent regulatory frameworks.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis of the pilot results, the following promising avenues for the further development of the Social and Legal Club (SLC) model within the secondary vocational education system can be identified.

Replication and Adaptation. The developed model and the associated set of methodological resources may be implemented in other secondary vocational education institutions with a legal profile. One potential approach involves comparing the model's performance across institutions with different levels of resource availability.

Digitization of Activities. The introduction of digital student portfolios for competence monitoring, online platforms for consultations and appointment scheduling, and specialized CRM systems for case management will contribute to increasing the effectiveness, transparency, and scalability of club activities.

Expansion of Network Interaction. Strengthening cooperation with government agencies and civil society organizations may facilitate the establishment of a comprehensive legal support ecosystem for the population. In addition, the development of "University–SVE" partnership formats, in which university-based legal clinics act as resource centers for SVE clubs, represents an effective direction for deepening institutional collaboration. Forming alliances with state legal bureaus, notarial offices, and bar associations will also enable the referral of complex cases to qualified specialists [3].

Development of Project and Grant Activities. Active participation in competitive grant programs and the attraction of external funding will allow clubs to enhance their technical and material base and implement socially significant initiatives.

According to the conducted research and its pilot implementation, a social and legal club founded on a systemic management model evolves from an episodic initiative into a sustainable institutional component of the secondary vocational education system. Such a model effectively fulfills two key objectives: it supports the training of competitive mid-level specialists through high-quality, practice-oriented education and significantly contributes to ensuring access to free legal aid for socially disadvantaged population groups. Based on a multi-level mentoring system and a project-based approach, the integrative model demonstrates substantial replicability potential and represents a promising direction for the development of legal education, as well as for the enhancement of Uzbekistan's social and legal services system.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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